

Distributions of Fatigue Life and Fatigue Strength in Notched Specimens of a Carbon Eight-Harness-Satin Laminate

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this research is to investigate the distribution properties of fatigue life and fatigue strength in sharply notched specimens of a carbon fabric laminate, which was made of three layers of eight-harness-satin/epoxy prepreg sheets. Fatigue life distributions were obtained at six stress levels by carefully designed fatigue tests of four point plane bending under a constant temperature and humidity condition. Sample sizes were 30 for the three high stress levels and 12 for the three low stress levels. The amount of scatter and distributional form of fatigue life and fatigue strength are discussed from the test results. It is found that fatigue strength distributions are practically normal and their standard deviations are constant regardless of fatigue life.

INTRODUCTION

The application of advanced composites for aircraft structures is very actively being developed in the U.S.A., Europe, and Japan for the purposes of reducing structural weight, saving fuel, and improving performance. Production parts made by advanced composites in civil aircraft are still limited in secondary structures. However, several prototypes of primary composite structures have been made and some of them are under flight testing.

These primary structures are of carbon/epoxy composites (CFRP). A lot of problems in using CFRP for production primary structure in civil aircraft have been left unsolved. CFRP's fatigue reliability is one of the most important problems, because composite structure is still difficult to be produced so homogeneously as metallic structure. A few data with respect to the amount of scatter and distributional form of CFRP's fatigue life have been published [1-7]; however, total information available is quite insufficient. These data are of small sample size or limited in a narrow stress level range. The scattering of CFRP's fatigue life is generally much larger than that of aluminum alloy's fatigue life and its distributional form does not necessarily fit the log-normal or two-parameter Weibull distribution. In order to use CFRP for production primary structure of civil aircraft, much more information concerning fatigue life distribution properties should be accumulated.

In the present investigation sharply notched specimens of a carbon eight-

harness-satin/epoxy laminate, of which fatigue behavior is expected to be different from that of unidirectional fiber laminate specimens, were fatigue tested under plane bending. Their fatigue life distributions were obtained in a wide stress level range. This paper discusses four items: (1) fatigue damage accumulation and stiffness reduction, (2) fatigue life distributions, (3) the median S-N relation, and (4) fatigue strength distributions and P-S-N curves. Some of these results are compared with those of 2024-T4 aluminum alloy [8], which is one of aircraft structural metals to be replaced by CFRP.

SPECIMEN AND METHOD OF TESTING

A carbon eight-harness-satin laminate was made of three layers of Mitsubishi Rayon S 410 prepreg sheets arranged in the same warp direction. Five laminate panels were manufactured at Mitsubishi Rayon, Ltd. on a hot plate with compression one by one under an identical cure cycle and trimmed to the size of 300mm×300mm. Composite specifications and mechanical properties are listed in Table I and the cure cycle in Table II.

Table I Composite design specifications and mechanical properties.

Prepreg physical property ^a		Laminate ^b { 3-ply in warp direc. (head/head/tail) }			
Prepreg system	S 410 (8-harness-satin)	Property	Mean	c.v. ^c %	m ^d
Ply thickness	0.40 mm	Thickness	1.14 mm	2.0	270
Resin content	40 ± 4 wt %	Tensile strength	612 MPa	2.1	5
Mass/unit	720 g/m ²	Tensile modulus	66 GPa	2.1	8
		Strain at failure	1.0 %	3.0	5
		Flexural modulus	77 GPa	1.9	7

^aCatalogue data by Mitsubishi Rayon, Ltd. ^cCoefficient of variation
^bProduced by Mitsubishi Rayon, Ltd. ^dSample size

Fig. 1 Specimen configuration in mm.

Table II Composite cure cycle.

Process	Pressure (kPa)	Temperature (°C)	Holding time (minute)
Cure	---	177	5
	686	177	120
Postcure	---	204	120

Fig. 1 illustrates the specimen configuration. The theoretical stress concentration factor K_t is approximately 8.7 in tension, which is calculated for a homogeneous isotropic elastic material. The test section is 30mm long and its center is notched. Rectangular specimen blanks were machined by a diamond cutter, with the warp direction longitudinal. The notch was first drilling $\phi 2.5$ and saw cutting with a fret saw machine having an electro-magnetic exciter, with carefull operation not to give any undesirable damage in the vicinity of the notch.

A conventional sub-resonant fatigue machine operating at a frequency of 30Hz was employed. All fatigue tests with constant amplitude loading were performed by only one fatigue machine. Specimens were loaded in fully reversed plane bending by a four point bending fixture. This machine was driven by a synchronous motor and some overloads were originally observed during several seconds after the start of operation. In order to prevent these overloads, a flywheel of about 2.4 kg was attached directly to the motor and a brake was used during a few seconds after the machine was switched on. The overloads were completely removed by these devices. The electricity of constant frequency and voltage supplied from a special power equipment having a quartz oscillator was used for driving the synchronous motor.

The temperature and relative humidity in the laboratory were kept within the ranges of 22 to 24°C and 50 to 55% respectively. Other experimental conditions

were carefully controlled not to cause additional scatter in fatigue life distribution.

TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stress Amplitude Representation

Nominal stress amplitude S represented by

$$S = 6M/bt^2, \tag{1}$$

which is given in a homogeneous isotropic elastic material, is used in this paper. M is the bending moment loaded to the specimen, b the net specimen width, and t the specimen thickness. The thickness of each specimen was measured and the moment was adjusted so as to give the fixed nominal stress amplitude to the specimen.

Fatigue Damage Accumulation and Stiffness Reduction

Fatigue damage accumulation in a specimen observed by the eye is as follows. The separation of a warp and a weft in the surface fabric occurred at the notch tip at first. This separation stopped at the crossover section of both tows, where a warp passed under a weft. The separation of this type propagated gradually warp by warp in the weft direction, and macroscopically, the deltoid damaged area was formed from the notch tip, as the top of the delta, to the side of the specimen. This behavior was observed in the four identical positions in a specimen. This damage accumulation reduced the stiffness and increased the strain amplitude in the net area section. When this strain reached the strain limit of the specimen, fiber fractures occurred in a moment, i.e., the specimen fracture at the same time. In the tests the propagation of delamination could not be confirmed and the gradual propagation of fiber fractures was not found. Such fatigue life as the amplitude of the reciprocating platen of the fatigue machine reached its limit due to the stiffness reduction of the specimen was not observed either. This kind of fatigue life frequently occurred in a unidirectional fiber laminate [7]. Therefore, fatigue life is defined by specimen fracture in this paper.

Let the stiffness of a rectangular specimen without a notch be EI , the residual stiffness ratio $EI/(EI)_0$ can be represented [7] as

$$EI/(EI)_0 \doteq a_0/a \tag{2}$$

where a is the amplitude of the reciprocating platen and sub-zero means "at the start of testing." The residual stiffness ratio of Eq. (2) can be used as the measure of the fatigue damage accumulation in a notched specimen. Fig. 2 illustrates the residual stiffness ratio $EI/(EI)_0$ versus the cycle ratio n/N obtained at six stress levels, where n is the number of stress cycles and N the number of cycles to failure. The stiffness of a specimen decreases a few percent rapidly within 5% of the specimen life and show a slow, linear reduction by about 20% until approximately 90% of the specimen life, then a quick reduction to fracture. The residual stiffness ratio 70% is judged to be just before the

Fig. 2 Stiffness reduction versus cycle ratio.

specimen fracture. Fig. 2 shows that the relationship between the residual stiffness ratio and the cycle ratio is independent of stress levels. This property is favorable in using a specific stiffness reduction ratio as a design criterion.

Fatigue Life Distributions

Fatigue life tests were conducted at six stress levels. Sample sizes denoted by *m* are 30 for the three high stress levels, i.e., *S*=363(37.0), 324(33.0), and 284(29.0)MPa(kgf/mm²), and 12 for the three low stress levels, i.e., *S*=265(27.0), 255(26.0), and 245(25.0)MPa(kgf/mm²). Nearly equal number of specimens in the tests at one stress level were randomly selected from the five laminate panels each. The test results of fatigue life *N* are presented in Fig. 3, log-normal and Weibull probability paper. The plotting positions in Fig. 3 are the median ranks. It is necessary to use the same plotting positions in comparing the data fitness to both distribution models. Table III indicates the median fatigue life and the estimated parameters for the log-normal and two-parameter Weibull distributions. In the log-normal distribution the parameters were estimated by the moments method for complete samples and by a graphical technique, i.e., the median ranks and the least square method, for the incomplete sample. In the two-parameter Weibull distribution the latter graphical technique was used.

Fig. 3 Fatigue life distributions.

Table III Median fatigue life and estimated parameters.

Stress <i>S</i> (MPa)	Sample size <i>m</i>	Median life \bar{N}	Log-normal		Weibull	
			Mean \bar{x}	Standard deviation σ_x	Shape parameter α	Scale parameter N_c
363	30	58 350	4.7438	0.1443	3.681	64 400
324	30	222 550	5.3516	0.1531	3.721	260 800
284	30	1 098 150	6.0455	0.1561	3.436	1 304 700
265	12	3 804 750	6.6405	0.2188	2.607	5 357 000
255	12 ^a	9 682 850	6.9512	0.2413	2.090	11 520 200
245	12(3)	16 516 600	7.1755	0.3696	1.645	19 209 300

^aNumber of specimens which did not fail

Distributional Form of Fatigue Life. The fatigue life distributions at the three high stress levels and *S*=255MPa fit well with the log-normal distribution. The log-normal distribution is acceptable for the fatigue life distribution at *S*=265MPa if the longest life is neglected. Owing to the shortest three lives, the fatigue life distribution at *S*=245MPa fits better with the two-parameter Weibull distribution than the log-normal distribution. Consequently, the log-normal distribution is better than the two-parameter Weibull distribution for the distribution model of fatigue life.

Scattering of Fatigue Life. The amount of fatigue life scatter is measured by the standard deviation of log-life or the shape parameter of the two-parameter Weibull distribution, and their estimates, σ_L and α respectively, are listed in Table III. The amount of fatigue life scatter is considered to be constant at the three high stress levels. It at the three low stress levels is larger than that at the three high stress levels, and becomes larger as the stress level is lowered. The fatigue life scattering obtained in this paper is comprehensively very small in comparison with that reported in Refs. [1-7].

Median S-N Curve

The data of the median S-N relation in Table III are plotted in Fig. 4 of semi-logarithmic graph paper. The median S-N curve drawn in Fig. 4 is fitted with the data by eye measurement.

The authors [8-9] have pointed out the empirical rule between the median S-N curve in the vicinity of the applied stress level on semi-logarithmic graph paper and the distribution of fatigue life in aluminum alloys and steels as follows. The distributional form of fatigue life is closely related to the shape of the median S-N curve, namely, the distributional form of fatigue life is log-normal where the median S-N curve is practically linear, and its skew is pronounced in the range where the slope of the median S-N curve changes rapidly. The amount of fatigue life scatter has a close relationship with the slope of the median S-N curve, i.e., the amount of fatigue life scatter is constant while the slope of the median S-N curve is equal, and becomes larger as the slope is gentler. The results at the three high stress levels and $S=255\text{MPa}$ fit well with this empirical rule. The agreement of the results at the other two low stress levels with this empirical rule is unclear. This may come from the small sample size. However, the empirical rule is effective in the sense that the amount of fatigue life scatter is larger than that at the three high stress levels due to the gentler slope of the median S-N curve.

Fig. 4 compares this median S-N curve with those of unidirectional carbon fiber composite specimens (AS/3501, 8-ply $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$, $K_t=8.7$) [7] and an aluminum alloy specimens (2024-T4, $K_t=8.25$) [8]. The difference in the median fatigue strength between the two composites is small and negligible. The median fatigue strength of eight-harness-satin laminate is about 2.3 times at $N=10^5$, 3.2 times at $N=10^6$, and 4.0 times at $N=10^7$ that of 2024-T4.

Fig. 4 Comparison of median S-N curves.

Table IV Equation of the median S-N relation approximated by two straight lines on semi-logarithmic graph paper.

Stress range (MPa)	Life range (cycle)	Equation
380 ~ 280	$3 \times 10^4 \sim 1.2 \times 10^6$	$S = -61.55 \log N + 655.0$
280 ~ 240	$1.2 \times 10^6 \sim 2 \times 10^7$	$S = -30.76 \log N + 468.1$

An analytical expression of the median S-N relation is necessary to discuss P-S-N curves in the next section. Fig. 4 suggests that two straight lines in the high and low stress level ranges can approximate well with the median S-N data. The equations of the two straight lines are provided in Table IV.

Fatigue Strength Distributions and P-S-N Curves

The scattering of fatigue life in CFRP is very large, but that of fatigue strength is not so large in general. This means that in fatigue designing a CFRP structure or planning on its certification test fatigue strength can be more easily used than fatigue life. Therefore, fatigue strength distributions are derived from the fatigue life data and P-S-N curves are determined.

As described before, at the three high stress levels the distributional form of fatigue life fit well with the log-normal distribution and the standard deviation of log-life is considered to be constant. Moreover, the median S-N relation in this stress range can be represented by a straight line on semi-logarithmic graph paper. It is clear from the P-S-N relation in this case that the distributional form of fatigue strength is normal and the standard deviation of fatigue strength σ_s is constant irrespective of fatigue life. The value of σ_s can be calculated from the slope of the median S-N curve a and the standard deviation of log-life σ_L as

$$\sigma_s = a\sigma_L, \tag{3}$$

where a is taken by absolute value. The standard deviation of log-life σ_L , which is considered to be constant regardless of stress levels, is given in terms of the pooled variance of the measurements as

$$\sigma_L = \sqrt{\Sigma (m_i - 1) \sigma_{L_i}^2 / \Sigma (m_i - 1)}. \tag{4}$$

σ_L is calculated to be 0.151 by using m_i and σ_{L_i} values in Table III. As $a=61.55$ from Table IV, Eq. (3) provides $\sigma_s=9.31\text{MPa}$.

Since at the three low stress levels the sample size is only 12 and the amount of fatigue life scatter is large, the fatigue life distributions obtained are not so simple as those at the three high stress levels. Consequently, instead of transforming the P-S-N relation, which are derived from fatigue life distributions, to fatigue strength distributions, the mean and standard deviation of fatigue strength are estimated by the Probit method [10]. This method involves the assumption that the fatigue strength distribution is normal. However, this assumption may have its validity as the extrapolation of the normal distribution of fatigue strength in the short life region corresponding to the three high stress levels. The mean and standard deviation are estimated by using the fatigue life data at the three low stress levels and plotted in Fig. 5. Fig. 5 also illustrates the median fatigue life data in Table III and the median S-N line drawn by the equation provided in Table IV. Fig. 5 indicates that the means of

Fig. 5 Mean and standard deviation of fatigue strength estimated by the Probit method.

fatigue strength agree well with the median S-N line, and the standard deviation of fatigue strength is about 10MPa regardless of fatigue life.

As described above, the standard deviation of fatigue strength is about 9.3 MPa in the short life region and about 10MPa in the long life region; therefore, 10MPa is acceptable for the whole life region. The properties that the distribution of fatigue strength is practically normal and its standard deviation is constant regardless of fatigue life are similar to those of 2024-T4 aluminum alloy and desirable for engineering use. The standard deviation of 10MPa is about 3 times that of 2024-T4 aluminum alloy. The coefficient of variation of fatigue strength of this fabric laminate is equal to or less than that of 2024-T4 for fatigue life larger than 10^6 , because the median fatigue strength of this fabric laminate is more than 3 times that of 2024-T4 for this life region. The results described above and the comparison of the median S-N curves in the preceding section prove this fabric laminate to be advantageous as a substitute material for 2024-T4 aluminum alloy.

The P-S-N curves can be easily derived from the median S-N equation provided in Table IV and the distribution model of fatigue strength, namely, of which distribution shape is normal and standard deviation σ_s is 10MPa regardless of fatigue life. Let the median S-N equation $S=f(N)$, the P-S-N relation corresponding to the probability of failure P is represented as

$$S_p = f(N) + t_p \sigma_s, \quad (5)$$

where t_p is the standard normal variable corresponding to P. Fig. 6 illustrates the P-S-N curves derived and the fatigue life data. These P-S-N curves express the fatigue life data well and are considered to be sufficient for practical use.

Fig. 6 P-S-N curves and fatigue life data.

CONCLUSIONS

The distributions of fatigue life and fatigue strength in sharply notched specimens of a carbon eight-harness-satin laminate were investigated. The results obtained are as follows:

- (1) According to eye-observation on fatigue damage accumulation, the separation of a warp and a weft in the surface fabric was pronounced, and the propagation of delamination was not confirmed. Fiber fractures were not found in the damage accumulation process and occurred at the final specimen fracture.
- (2) The stiffness of a specimen decreased a few percent rapidly within 5% of the specimen life, and showed a slow, linear reduction by about 20% until approximately 90% of the specimen life, then quickly reduced to fracture. The relationship between the residual stiffness ratio and the cycle ratio was practically independent of stress levels.

(3) The log-normal distribution was generally better than the two-parameter Weibull distribution for the distribution model of fatigue life.

(4) In the stress level range from $S=284$ to 363MPa , the fatigue life scattering was invariant and the standard deviation of log-life was roughly 0.15. The amount of fatigue life scatter obtained in the present paper was comprehensively very small in comparison with the data of CFRP reported in Refs. [1-7].

(5) The empirical rule between fatigue life distributions and the median S-N curve on semi-logarithmic graph paper pointed out in metals by the authors fit fairly well the test results.

(6) Fatigue strength distributions in the short life region corresponding to the three high stress levels were of normal with standard deviation about 9.3 MPa and independent of fatigue life. In the long life region corresponding to the three low stress levels, the standard deviation of fatigue strength estimated by the Probit method were about 10MPa regardless of fatigue life.

(7) The P-S-N curves were drawn using the fatigue strength distribution model, which is a normal distribution with standard deviation 10MPa regardless of fatigue life, and the median S-N relation approximated by two straight lines on semi-logarithmic graph paper. They fit the fatigue life data well and were considered to be sufficient for practical use.

(8) The median fatigue strength was 2 to 4 times that of 2024-T4 aluminum alloy for the life range from 10^5 to 10^7 . The standard deviation of fatigue strength was about 3 times that of 2024-T4 aluminum alloy.

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